

Speculation on Special Relativity and Wave Behaviour for a Photon and Free Particle Part 2

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Oct. 26, 2024

In Part I, we showed that one may begin with a rest mass, m_0 , at rest at $x=0$, t and obtain a Lorentz transformation which includes the factor $1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$. "c" was said to be a constant and upper bound on v . If one assumes that c is frame independent, one has a special object we will call a photon to give it a name. We argue that using $x-x_0 = c(t-t_0)$ for this object and $E=pc$ which follows from $E=mc\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ and $p=mv/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ for $v \rightarrow c$, and also the Lorentz transformation, one obtains $p(x-x_0) = E(t-t_0)$ ((1)) which holds in all frames. Given that $E/p=c$, one has the classical wave equation, $v = \text{frequency} \times \text{wavelength}$, if one calls $x-x_0$ the wavelength and $t-t_0$ the period. Thus, this object with speed c in all frames moves like a classical wave and has a wavelength and frequency, but also as a deterministic object. The wave feature suggests the possibility of the photon undergoing interference

We argued in Part I that it is of particular importance that special relativity holds for both photons and particles with rest mass moving at constant speed. (Here we only consider particles moving at constant v so we can compare them to photons as done in Part I.) For the photon, the wave features are linked both with motion in spacetime with speed c and with time and space gradations of $\text{constant}/E$ and $\text{constant}/p$ as shown in ((1)). Although $E/p=c$, we suggest that it is the gradations depending on $\text{constant}/p$ and $\text{constant}/E$ which are important. These define natural intervals in which one does not follow the particle deterministically, we argue. To obtain an equation identical to ((1)) for a particle with rest mass, so that it is on the same footing as the photon, one must use: $dA = 0 = -Et + px$, where $dA=0$ because A is a Lorentz invariant. In other words, this suggests that a particle with rest mass also has dx and dt regions of uncertainty which means that there should be probabilistic and not deterministic interactions at lengths $dx = \text{constant}/p$. In other words, a particle with rest mass may interfere with a 2-slit system if the slits are separated by \hbar/p .

Lorentz Transformation

In Part I, we suggested creating a 2x2 Lorentz matrix:

$$\begin{vmatrix} g(v) & vg(v) \\ vg & g \end{vmatrix} \quad ((2))$$

where $g=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ ((3))

Here c is an unknown constant speed. If one assumes that it is the same in all frames and corresponds to an object, then using:

$E=mc\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ and $p=mv/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ for $v \rightarrow c$ yields:

$E=pc$ for this object which we call a photon to give it a name. At this point, there is no notion of a photon having wavelike properties.

Next, we consider the deterministic equation: $x-ct = x_0 - ct_0$ ((4))

If one multiplies by p , one obtains: $px-Et = p(x_0-ct_0)$ ((5))

((5)) must hold in all frames, i.e. be a Lorentz invariant. One may see this is the case, by using $x_0=0$ with $E=pc$ so that: $p' = \gamma p(c+v)$ and $x_0'= \gamma v t_0$ and $t_0' = \gamma t_0$.

Then: $p'x' - E't' = p'(x_0'-ct_0') = p t_0$.

One may rewrite ((5)) as: $p(x-x_0) = E(t-t_0)$ ((6))

We note that ((6)) only holds for $E=pc$ and has not been derived for the particle with rest mass for which one has $E^2 = p^2 c^2 + m_0^2 c^4$ ($c=1$). If one uses $E/p=c$, then ((6)) is identical to a classical wave equation. In other words, deterministic motion with speed c matches the speed of the wave. In other words, there is a duality for the photon with both viewpoints using the same speed.

Treating the Photon and Particle with Rest Mass in a Similar Fashion

We argue that the photon emerges from the theory explaining a particle with rest mass, with both having E, p, x, t . We thus suggest that there should be an analogous form for ((6)) for a particle with rest mass. In fact, if one considers both a particle with rest mass and a photon only in terms of E, p, x, t , then ((6)) should really hold for both, but ((6)) was only derived for $E=pc$ explicitly

To find an equation analogous to ((6)) one may use:

$$A = -Et+px \rightarrow dA=0 \text{ (Lorentz invariant)} = -E dt + p dx \text{ ((7))}$$

In the photon case, ((6)) emerged from only using $A = p(x_0-ct_0)$, but for a particle with rest mass, one may use ((7)) to obtain an analogous relation. We suggest, however, that the comparison allows one to consider dx and dt in ((7)) as equivalent to $x-x_0$ and $t-t_0$ for a photon. This in turn suggests a wavelength region for a particle with rest mass given by $constant/p$ and a period given by $constant.E$ even though a particle with rest mass does not satisfy the classical wave equation $v= \text{frequency} * \text{wavelength}$, while a photon does. The uncertain or probabilistic regions dx and dt exist for both. We call these regions probabilistic because both are associated with interference. One does not know in a probabilistic manner how the photon or particle with rest mass will interact in such a region, i.e. it could interact with both slits in a 2-slit apparatus with slits separated by about \hbar/p .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider an object with constant speed c in all frames as emerging from Lorentz transformations equations applied only to a particle with rest mass. We call this new

object a photon to give it a name and note that it seems to be a deterministic particle with no wave properties. We then use: $x-x_0 = c(t-t_0)$ (deterministic equation) and multiply by p , noting that $E = \gamma m_0 c^2$ and $p = \gamma m_0 v$ yield $E = pc$ in the limit $v \rightarrow c$. Then: $px - Et = p(x_0 - ct_0)$ is an invariant equation with $A = p(x_0 - ct_0)$ being a Lorentz invariant. The point we make is that this equation may be written as: $p(x-x_0) = E(t-t_0)$ which is equivalent to a classical wave equation with the wave moving with speed c just like the deterministic photon. In other words, there is a length region of constant $\lambda = (x-x_0)$ in which probabilistic and not deterministic interactions may occur, i.e. interference with a 2-slit apparatus if the slits are about λ apart.

We suggest that given that a photon emerges from a theory of a particle with rest mass, one would expect a $p(x-x_0) = E(t-t_0)$ type equation to also apply to this particle as it is also described by E, p, x, t , but the equation was explicitly derived for a particle with $E = pc$. If, however, one uses: $A = -Et + px$ where A is a Lorentz invariant, then $dA = 0 = -E dt + p dx$. One may then identify dt with λ/E and $t-t_0$ and dx with λ/p and $x-x_0$. In other words, even a particle with rest mass may have an uncertainty region $\Delta x = \lambda/p$ in which probabilistic and not deterministic interactions occur even though it satisfies neither $E = pc$ or $v = \text{frequency} \times \text{wavelength}$. This suggests a particle with rest mass undergoing interference from a 2-slit apparatus if the slits are separated by about λ .